

A postcard from the future: Tools and services from a perfect DMP world

Monday 20th February 2017, 9:00am - 12:30pm

Room: Wolfson A, Quincentenary Conference Centre

The Royal College of Surgeons of Edinburgh, Nicolson Street, EH8 9DW

Data management plans (DMPs) are a thing mostly thanks to research funders requiring them with grant proposals. But the current manifestation of a DMP—a static pdf/doc/txt file created before a project even begins—only contributes to the perception that they're an annoying administrative exercise. What they really are is an integral part of research practice since today most research (across all disciplines) involves data, code, and other digital components. So can we reimagine DMPs in this context?

How do researchers manage information? What tools and processes are already in use? If we assume that DMPs are here for good, then how do we position them in existing workflows and convert them into something useful, a tool for improving research practice and ensuring FAIR data comes out at the end?

Where are we now regarding DMPs and data sharing? Where will we be in 2 years? 5 years? 10 years? Peering into the future we can anticipate enforced mandates and OA2020 in Europe and beyond...

We know better data management is possible and think that better DMP infrastructure that serves as an educational platform and hooks into other systems is part of the solution. We happen to have a piece of DMP infrastructure with a decent level of adoption that we want to use for experimentation. Our larger goal, though, is to connect stakeholders, foster consensus where appropriate/necessary, make this a collaborative and community-driven effort, make sure everyone understands the problems and then work together to solve them.

Registration opens at 8:15am Please arrive early so we can start at 9am		
09:00	Intro on workshop aims and scope	Stephanie Simms (UC3) & Sarah Jones (DCC)
09:05	Demo of the INDIGO-DataCloud system	Fernando Aguilar Gómez, IFCA
09:20	Demo of life science Data Stewardship wizard	Rob Hooft, DTL
09:35	Activity: where do DMPs sit in the lifecycle and what systems could be integrated Mind map typical workflows, highlighting tools and systems that interface with DMPs and which data could be fed automatically from other systems into DMPs or vice versa?	All

10:20	<p>Group discussion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which systems/services should connect with DMP tools? • What can be automated and what will always have to be completed manually? • Workflows for DMPs - consider pathways to sharing/publishing/discovering... • How can we bring DMPs closer to data (e.g., should we package DMPs together with data)? 	
10:45	Coffee	
11:00	Active Data Management Plans – a vision of what could be achieved	Tomasz Miksa, TU Wien
11:15	<p>Activity: Machine-actionable use cases</p> <p>Join tables based on the most popular topics noted below. In groups, define a use case(s) for the theme proposed and identify requirements. Prioritise these requirements considering what would add most value and is feasible in current circumstances.</p>	All
12:15	DMP Roadmap project update	Stephanie Simms (UC3) & Sarah Jones (DCC)
12:30	Lunch	